

EFFECT OF EPOXY CURING ON TILTED FIBER BRAGG GRATINGS TRANSMISSION SPECTRUM

D. Kinet^{1*}, C. Caucheteur¹, M. Wuilpart¹, D. Garray², F. Narbonneau³, P. Mégret¹

¹ Mons University, Electromagnetism and Telecom Unit, Bld Dolez 31, 7000 Mons, Belgium

² Sirris, Materials Engineering Department, Rue Bois Saint Jean 12, 4102 Seraing, Belgium

³ Multitel, Applied Photonics Departement, Rue Pierre et Marie Curie 2, 7000 Mons, Belgium

* (damien.kinet@umons.ac.be)

Keywords: *Tilted Fiber Bragg Grating, Epoxy curing*

1 Abstract

We present the spectral evolution of a tilted fiber Bragg grating (TFBG) during the curing of an epoxy used in the fabrication of composite materials. A differential shift of the cladding modes is associated to a modification of the surrounding refractive index (SRI), which can be used as an indicator of the epoxy polymerization state.

2 Introduction

In the food industry, in biomedical applications or for process monitoring, there is a need to measure the refractive index. Commercial refractometers available on the market, derived from the Abbe configuration, yield a very accurate value of the refractive index (typically 10^{-6}). However, the size and the power requirement of this kind of device limit their operation for in situ measurements. It is the reason why refractometers based on fiber gratings technology have been widely developed since more than ten years. Due to their small dimensions, their electromagnetic interference immunity and their high mechanical resistance, it becomes natural to embed fiber Bragg gratings (FBGs) sensors into composite material pieces to monitor their behavior when they are subject to stresses. Indeed, it has been demonstrated that the optical fiber embedding can be done without modifying their mechanical resistance [1-2]. However, for some applications, there is an additional need to collect parameters information during the realization process of composite materials. Epoxy polymerization percentage is one of them. Indeed, a uniform and complete polymerization is one of the requirements to obtain a high quality final product. Different optical fiber based techniques allow measuring the evolution of the surrounding refractive index (SRI). The most

known is based on the Fresnel reflection evolution at the end of a cleaved optical fiber [3-4]. While this technique made its proofs and allows to measure an SRI variation over a wide band, it does not give temperature and strain information. Long period fiber gratings (LPFG) consist in a periodic refractive index modulation of the core of an optical fiber that couples the guided core mode towards co-propagating cladding modes. The modes are lossy and the transmission spectrum of an LPFG contains a number of attenuation bands. The refractive index sensitivity of LPFGs arises from the refractive index dependence of the coupling wavelength upon the effective index of the cladding mode [4-6]. By tracking several dips of the transmission spectrum, it is possible to have a sensor with a high refractive index sensitivity over a wide range even at high SRI. However, it also has some drawbacks: high bend, strain and temperature sensitivities strongly depending of the optical fiber parameters. While uniform FBGs are good temperature and pressure sensors, they are not sensitive to the SRI, which prevents their use to characterize the polymerization of the epoxy. In this work, we demonstrate that a tilted FBG (TFBG) can be used during the polymerization of the epoxy, as it presents a high sensitivity to SRI variations. Usually, when a TFBG is used, the refractive index estimation is based on measuring the normalized envelope of the cladding-mode resonance spectrum in transmission. This parameter being relatively insensitive to temperature, it presents an important advantage comparatively to LPFGs. However, in the case of epoxy curing, non-uniform constraints can also appear inducing modification of the cladding-mode envelope shape and so of the estimated value of the SRI. By tracking the wavelength shift of the Bragg peak and one cladding mode resonance, we have found a differential evolution that is attributed to an

SRI modification due to the polymerization of the epoxy. In this case, if there is a non-uniform strain applied on the sensor during the curing, this one will affect the Bragg peak shape, which is directly observed in the amplitude spectrum.

3 Theory

TFBGs enhance the backward coupling of light from the fiber core to the cladding and are therefore sensitive to the SRI [6]. To retrieve the information about an external perturbation (temperature, strain, SRI...), an accurate method consists in tracking the wavelengths of the cladding modes [7-8]. Contrary to the core mode resonance, these modes are indeed sensitive to SRI in addition to temperature and strain. Eq. (1) and (2) present the Bragg wavelength and cladding modes dependence on temperature, strain and SRI variations.

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = \alpha_B\Delta T + \beta_B\varepsilon \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_{cl,i}}{\lambda_{cl,i}} = \alpha_{cl,i}\Delta T + \beta_{cl,i}\varepsilon + \gamma_{cl,i}\Delta SRI \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\lambda_B$ and $\Delta\lambda_{cl,i}$ are the wavelength shifts of the Bragg and the i^{th} cladding mode resonances, respectively. The shifts take their origin from a variation of temperature (ΔT), strain (ε) and/or surrounding refractive index (ΔSRI). The thermal coefficients (α_B and $\alpha_{cl,i}$) are roughly identical whereas the strain coefficient β_B is different from $\beta_{cl,i}$, which also depends on the considered mode (i).

4 Experiments and results

For our experiments, we have used a 6 mm long 4° TFBG written into hydrogen-loaded standard singlemode fiber by means of a double frequency Argon laser emitting at 244 nm through a 1095.04 nm-period uniform phase mask. Fig. 1 shows the transmission spectrum of our TFBG after inscription with its different sensitive regions. The Bragg peak, finding its origin in the coupling of the forward core mode to the backward core mode, is insensitive to the external refractive index. The TFBG was placed in a recipient containing an epoxy. The epoxy resulted from two different chemicals: Araldite XB3585 for the resin and Aradur HY2954 for the

hardener. The curing time cycle lasts 1 hour at 80°C and then 8 hours at 140°C.

Fig. 2 is a schematic view of the interrogation set-up. It is composed of a broadband source and a high-resolution optical spectrum analyzer Ando AQ6317C. The TFBG was placed inside an oven. Equipments are driven by computer. Fig. 3 displays a picture of our final sample (TFBG in the cured epoxy). Fig. 4 shows the TFBG spectrum at different times of the curing process. The trace “0h00”, “0h08”, “8h01” and “20h03” are TFBG spectra in the air, embedded in the epoxy at ambient temperature, embedded in the epoxy at 140°C, and at the end of the curing (ambient temperature), respectively. When the TFBG is placed in the epoxy, some cladding modes become radiated while the rest undergoes a wavelength shift depending on the cladding mode order. At the end of the curing, the TFBG is compressed (the spectrum is blue shifted at 2.9nm). On Fig. 5, we shifted the whole spectrum to make the Bragg wavelength peaks coincide. By zooming on the Bragg peak (see Fig. 6), we can deduce that the TFBG undergoes a uniform axial compression without other perturbation, as the Bragg peak shape is not deformed. A close look at a particular cladding mode resonance after repositioning pinpoints a wavelength shift, as illustrated in Fig. 7. This shift, around 72pm between the beginning and the end of curing at the same temperature, results from both a differential strain sensitivity compared to the Bragg peak and an SRI variation (Eq. 1 and 2). Fig. 8 presents the wavelength shift of this cladding mode and the Bragg peak during the curing after repositioning. The corresponding temperature evolution is also plotted. A wavelength shift of the cladding mode (~72 pm), at a same temperature, between the beginning of the process and the end of the curing is observed (dots 1 and 2 on Fig. 8). Thanks to the Bragg peak, we can estimate the strain induced by the curing (Eq. 1). Indeed, a blue shift of the Bragg peak of 2.9 nm, combined with a strain sensitivity of our FBG of 1.08 pm/ $\mu\varepsilon$, we find that at the end of the curing, the TFBG undergoes a compression of 2680 $\mu\varepsilon$. From this value, we can evaluate the contribution of the SRI variation to the wavelength shift of the cladding mode (~ 40 pm). Indeed, from [8], we can graphically calculate that a strain of 2680 $\mu\varepsilon$ will induce a differential wavelength shift

between the Bragg peak and this particular cladding mode of ~ 32 pm. The use of a commercial software [9] allows deducing the SRI variation. On Fig. 9, we show the simulated behavior of the Bragg peak for different values of SRI at constant temperature. As expected, we can see that the Bragg peak is totally insensitive to a modification of the external refractive index. Indeed, the Bragg peak being due to the coupling of the forward core mode towards the backward core mode, it is impossible for the evanescent field of the guided mode to be exposed to the medium to be tested and so to be affected by this refractive index change. Fig. 10 shows that a variation of ~ 0.013 of the external refractive index is necessary to obtain a wavelength shift (~ 40 pm) of our cladding mode dip corresponding to the SRI variation contribution in the total wavelength shift of this cladding mode. This SRI variation is linked to the polymerization of the epoxy during the curing. On table 1, we present the main parameters and their values used to carry out our simulations.

5 Conclusion

We have studied the spectral behavior of a TFBG embedded into epoxy during a curing cycle. By tracking the wavelength shift of a cladding mode and the Bragg peak, we observe a differential variation of the first one that results from the SRI variation of the epoxy during the polymerization. TFBG is thus a promising approach for polymerization diagnostics.

Fig. 1. Initial spectrum of the TFBG with its main sensitive regions.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the interrogation set-up.

Fig. 3. The sample at the end of the curing.

Fig. 4. TFBG spectral evolution during epoxy curing (with offset in the vertical axis).

Fig. 5. Repositioning of the different spectra to obtain the matching between all Bragg wavelengths.

Fig. 6. Zoom on the Bragg peak after repositioning.

Fig. 7. Zoom on a cladding mode resonance after repositioning.

Fig. 8. Wavelength variation of a cladding mode dip (blue) and Bragg peak (green) after repositioning.

Fig. 9. Position of the Bragg peak for different values of SRI (numerical simulation).

Fig. 10. Position of one cladding mode for different values of SRI (numerical simulation).

Grating length [mm]	6
Refractive index modulation	4.65e-4
Core refractive index	1.45
Cladding refractive index	1.445
Grating period [nm]	547.52
Core radius [μm]	4.1
Cladding radius [μm]	62.5
SRI (wet – initial)	1.403
SRI (cured – final)	1.416

Table 1. Values used for the TFBG simulations.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by the European Regional Development Fund and Wallonia (Mediatic Project). The authors thank the Attraction Pole Program of Belgian Science Policy IPA6/10.

References

- [1] K. Satori, K. Fukuchi, Y. Kurosawa, A. Hongo and N. Takeda “Polyimide-coated small diameter optical fiber sensors for embedding in composite laminate structures”. *Sensory phenomena and measurement instrumentation for smart structures and materials*. Newport Beach, Etats-Unis, Vol. 4328, pp 285-294, 2001.
- [2] D. Kinet, D. Garray, M. Wuilpart, F. Dortu, X. Dusermont, D. Giannone, P. Mégret “Behaviour of optical fibre Bragg grating sensors embedded into composite material under flexion”. *14th European Conference on Composite Materials*, Budapest, Hungary, 442, pp.1-10, 2010.
- [3] T. Kosaka, D. Ueda, K. Ohsaka, Y. Sawada “Cure monitoring of UV chain curing polymer by fiber optic measurement of refractive index”. *16th International Conference on Composite Materials, ICCM-16*, Kyoto, Japan, 8-13 July, 2007.
- [4] S.J. Buggy, E. Chehura, S.W. James and R.P. Tatam “Optical fibre grating refractometers for resin cure monitoring”. *J.Opt.A: Pure Appl.Opt.*, Vol. 9, pp.S60-S65, 2007.
- [5] H. J. Patrick, A. D. Kersey, and F. Bucholtz, “Analysis of the response of long period fiber gratings to external index of refraction,” *J. Lightwave Technol.*, Vol.16, pp.1606-1612, 1998.
- [6] G. Laffont and P. Ferdinand “Tilted short-period fiber-Bragg-grating-induced coupling to cladding modes for accurate refractometry”. *Meas. Sci. Technol.*, 12, pp. 765-770, 2001.
- [7] C-F. Chan, C. Chen, A. Jafari, A. Laronche, D.J. Thomson and J. Albert, “Optical fiber refractometer using narrowband cladding-mode resonance shifts,” *Applied Optics* 46, pp.1142-1149, 2007.
- [8] C. Chen, L. Xiong, C. Caucheteur, P. Mégret and J. Albert “Differential strain sensitivity of high order cladding modes in weakly tilted fiber Bragg grating”. *Photonic Applications for Aerospace, Transportation, and Harsh Environments*, Boston, USA, Vol. 6379, 63790E, pp.1-7, 2006.
- [9] Optigrating, from the Optiwave Corporation (Ottawa, Canada).